

Section	Dimension	Item / Construct	Pre-interaction Mean \pm SD	Post-interaction Mean \pm SD	Direction of Change	Interpretation
4.1	Sustainability awareness	Environmental sustainability consideration — A1	3.33 \pm 1.37	3.75 \pm 1.06	Increased	Participants considered environmental impacts more after the chatbot interaction.
4.1	Sustainability awareness	Social sustainability consideration — A2	3.67 \pm 0.89	3.75 \pm 0.87	Slight increase	Social sustainability awareness improved modestly.
4.1	Sustainability awareness	Economic sustainability consideration — A3	3.83 \pm 1.19	4.25 \pm 0.62	Increased	Participants showed stronger consideration of economic sustainability.
4.1	Sustainability awareness	Sustainability as non-priority — A4 [R]	2.17 \pm 1.34	1.83 \pm 1.19	Decreased	Participants were less likely to treat sustainability as a low priority.
4.1	Sustainability awareness	Knowledge of environmental footprint evaluation —	3.25 \pm 1.36	3.67 \pm 0.78	Increased	Participants reported improved ability to

		A5				evaluate environmental footprint.
4.1	Sustainability awareness	Sustainability as someone else's responsibility — A6 [R]	2.08 ± 1.38	1.42 ± 0.67	Decreased	Participants showed stronger ownership of sustainability concerns.
4.2	Bias awareness	Awareness that biases influence software design — B1	4.00 ± 1.13	4.17 ± 0.72	Slight increase	Participants became more aware of cognitive biases in design decisions.
4.2	Bias awareness	Belief in objective reasoning — B2 [R]	3.25 ± 0.87	3.33 ± 0.99	Little/no improvement	A bias blind spot appeared to persist.
4.2	Bias awareness	Ability to recognise biases in own decisions — B3	3.17 ± 0.94	3.42 ± 1.17	Increased	Participants became more capable of recognising biases in their own work.
4.2	Bias awareness	Questioning one's own assumptions — B4 [R]	2.67 ± 0.99	2.42 ± 1.24	Decreased	Participants showed improved reflective questioning of

						assumptions.
4.3	AI-supported reflection	AI helps identify blind spots — C1	4.25 ± 0.62	4.50 ± 0.52	Increased	Positive attitudes toward AI-supported reflection became stronger.
4.3	AI-supported reflection	AI-driven questioning is not useful — C2 [R]	1.92 ± 0.90	1.75 ± 0.87	Decreased	Participants disagreed more strongly that AI questioning is not useful.
4.3	AI-supported reflection	Conversational AI supports critical reflection — C3	4.33 ± 0.49	4.58 ± 0.52	Increased	Participants rated conversational AI as more useful for reflection.
4.3	AI-supported reflection	Preference to reflect alone — C4 [R]	2.00 ± 0.85	1.67 ± 0.49	Decreased	Participants became more open to AI-assisted reflection.